

Evaluating Machine Learning Models for Key Soil Properties

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Abstract: Machine learning has become an essential tool in environmental sciences, offering faster and more cost-effective alternatives to traditional laboratory soil analysis. This study evaluates the potential of mid-infrared (MIR) and visible–near-infrared (Vis-NIR) soil spectroscopy combined with machine learning techniques to predict key soil attributes, such as clay, sand, soil organic carbon, calcium content, and cation exchange capacity. Three machine learning models were tested: partial least squares regression (PLSR), Cubist, and a one-dimensional convolutional neural network (1D CNN). Results show that models trained on MIR spectral data generally outperformed those based on Vis-NIR data, and that Cubist is the best-performing method on average. Out of 16 soil attributes that were analyzed, seven attributes were predicted with high accuracy ($R^2 > 0.9$), while only two attributes showed moderate performance (R^2 between 0.5 and 0.7). The findings demonstrate that combining soil spectroscopy with machine learning techniques provides a reliable and efficient alternative to conventional laboratory analysis for several key soil properties.

Keywords: soil spectroscopy; machine learning; partial least squares regression; cubist regression; convolutional neural network.

1 Introduction

Machine learning has become an indispensable asset in many human activities, and it has proven to be an efficient and powerful tool when used correctly. In soil science, one important area is the study of soil composition, which has traditionally been determined through time-consuming laboratory analysis of collected samples. An alternative approach is soil spectroscopy, which utilizes machine learning to estimate soil properties in a much faster and more cost-effective way. Soil spectroscopy is a technique that measures light absorption when light in certain regions of the electromagnetic spectrum is applied to the soil surface. Common regions used for soil spectroscopy are visible (Vis), near-infrared (NIR) and mid-infrared (MIR) regions of the electromagnetic spectrum. These characteristic spectra can then be used to predict various soil attributes, such as particle size distribution, mineral and organic compounds, and water (Woodwell Climate Research Center 2024).

A range of machine learning methods has been applied to this task. Partial least squares regression (PLSR) is among the most commonly applied techniques and has been successfully used to predict soil properties such as organic carbon, total carbon, nitrogen, pH, cation exchange capacity, and texture fractions using both mid-infrared (MIR) and visible–near-infrared (Vis-NIR) spectra (Baldock

et al. 2013, Madari et al. 2006, Stevens et al. 2008, Terhoeven-Urselmans et al. 2010, Wijewardane et al. 2018). Cubist regression has also demonstrated strong predictive capability and has been reported to outperform PLSR for certain soil attributes (Dangal et al. 2019, Ng et al. 2019). Large-scale benchmarking efforts, such as the Open Soil Spectral Library, which combines multiple soil spectral libraries, further confirm the competitiveness of PLSR and Cubist across numerous soil properties (Safanelli et al. 2025). Tree-based methods such as random forest have also been applied successfully, particularly for predicting soil organic carbon and other chemical properties (Dangal et al. 2019, Wadoux 2023). More recently, deep learning approaches have gained increasing attention (Romić et al. 2024). One-dimensional and two-dimensional convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have been evaluated for both regression and classification tasks, demonstrating promising performance for selected soil attributes (Kawamura et al. 2021, Ng et al. 2019, Padarian et al. 2019, Riese and Keller 2019).

Despite extensive research, many studies focus on a limited number of soil attributes or modeling approaches. Comprehensive benchmarking of machine learning models across a broad range of soil properties using both MIR and Vis-NIR data within a unified framework remains comparatively limited. This study evaluates the performance of three machine learning methods, PLSR, Cubist, and a one-dimensional convolutional neural network, in predicting 16 soil attributes using MIR and Vis-NIR spectral data.

This conference paper is based on the author's Master's thesis on soil parameter mapping using open Earth observation data and machine learning techniques (Avirović 2024). The paper presents a condensed and revised benchmarking study focused on comparing PLSR, Cubist, and 1D CNN models across 16 soil attributes using MIR and Vis-NIR spectral data.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Dataset

In this study, models were developed using the KSSL and LUCAS subsets of the Open Soil Spectral Library (OSSL), which were selected because they provide the largest number of relevant samples and represent the main geographic coverage of the dataset. The KSSL dataset includes 76,813 MIR samples and 19,807 Vis-NIR samples, while the LUCAS dataset provides 40,175 Vis-NIR samples (Safanelli et al. 2025, Woodwell Climate Research Center 2024). The MIR spectral data are reported in absorbance units per wavenumber and cover the range from 600 to

4000 cm^{-1} at 2 cm^{-1} resolution. The Vis-NIR spectra are reported in reflectance units per wavelength at a resolution of 2 nm, covering the spectral range between 350 and 2500 nm for the KSSL samples and between 400 and 2500 nm for the LUCAS samples. For Vis-NIR-based comparisons, LUCAS data were used where available, while KSSL Vis-NIR data were used only for soil attributes for which LUCAS Vis-NIR measurements were not available. Sixteen soil attributes were predicted, including texture fractions, carbon-related variables, pH, cation exchange capacity, bulk density, electrical conductivity, water retention, and selected nutrients. The full list of predicted soil attributes, corresponding dataset variables, and descriptive statistics is provided in Table 3 in Appendix A.

2.2 Machine learning methods

To predict the values of the 16 soil attributes, three machine learning methods were used: partial least squares regression (PLSR), Cubist, and a one-dimensional convolutional neural network (1D CNN). These machine learning techniques are commonly used modeling approaches to analyze spectral data. The PLSR method is a latent variable technique, Cubist is a rule-based regression algorithm, and 1D CNN is a deep learning algorithm that is capable of finding local patterns in the spectral data. This combination allows comparison between a traditional regression method for spectral data, an interpretable machine learning model, and a neural network model.

PLSR can handle multicollinearity among predictor variables by projecting the original variables into a smaller set of latent components, so it is commonly used for modeling high-dimensional spectral data. In this study, we set the number of latent variables to 120 because principal component analysis showed that the first 120 components explain 99.99% of the variance in both MIR and Vis-NIR spectra. Model performance was evaluated using 10-fold cross-validation.

Cubist is a rule-based regression method that combines decision trees with linear regression models. The spectral data were first reduced using principal component analysis, and the first 120 components were used as predictors. The number of committees was determined using 5-fold cross-validation on a subset of the data. Based on these tests and the recommendations from the Cubist documentation, five committees were used, and the number of rules was left at the default value of 500. To evaluate the performance of the Cubist model, we used a 10-fold cross-validation.

The one-dimensional CNN architecture used in this study is based on the design proposed by Ng et al. 2019. The network consists of four convolution–pooling blocks and two dense layers (Table 1). For models trained on Vis-NIR data, the filter size was reduced from 20 to 10 because the length of the MIR spectra is almost double the length of the Vis-NIR spectra. The spectral data were used directly as input without preprocessing. Models were trained using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.001 and mean squared error as the loss function. The dataset was split into 75% for training and 25% for validation. Models were

Table 1. The architecture of the neural network used.

Layer type	Filter size MIR/Vis-NIR	Number of filters	Activation function
Convolutional	20/10	32	ReLU
Max-pooling	2	-	-
Convolutional	20/10	64	ReLU
Max-pooling	5	-	-
Convolutional	20/10	128	ReLU
Max-pooling	5	-	-
Convolutional	20/10	256	ReLU
Max-pooling	5	-	-
Dropout (0.4)	-	-	-
Flatten	-	-	-
Fully connected	100	-	ReLU
Dropout (0.2)	-	-	-
Fully connected	1	-	Linear

trained for 20 epochs, but additional 20 epochs were used if the obtained performance was low with R^2 score less than 0.3.

2.3 Evaluation metrics

After training the models, to test their performance we calculated three different performance metrics: the mean squared error (MSE), the mean absolute error (MAE), and the coefficient of determination (R^2). MSE and MAE measure the magnitude of prediction errors and their values depend on the scale of the target variable, while R^2 measures the proportion of variance explained by the model and is scale independent. All three metrics were used to compare models trained to predict the same target variable, but to compare model performance across different soil attributes and different spectral datasets R^2 score was used. For MSE and MAE, lower values indicate better model performance, whereas higher R^2 values indicate better performance.

3 Results

A total of 84 models were developed to predict the values of 16 soil attributes using three machine learning algorithms and two types of spectral data. The performance of the models was evaluated using MSE, MAE, and R^2 , with R^2 used as the main metric for comparison. Overall, models trained on MIR spectral data generally outperformed those trained on Vis-NIR data. Among the evaluated methods, Cubist and the one-dimensional CNN achieved the best overall performance, while PLSR generally performed slightly worse. Several soil attributes, including organic carbon, total carbon, calcium carbonate, cation exchange capacity, clay, sand, and calcium, were predicted with high accuracy, with R^2 scores higher than 0.90. Models for nitrogen, pH, water retention, iron, silt, magnesium, and bulk density achieved R^2 values between 0.70 and 0.90. However, the predictions for electrical conductivity and potassium were less accurate, with R^2

Figure 1. Comparison of model performance across soil attributes based on R^2 scores for (a) MIR and (b) Vis-NIR spectral data. Bars show the performance of PLSR, Cubist, and 1D CNN models. The Vis-NIR panel includes only soil attributes for which Vis-NIR data were available in the selected datasets.

scores below 0.70 for all models. Figure 1 provides a visual comparison of R^2 scores across soil attributes, spectral data types, and machine learning methods. As shown in Table 2, all best-performing models for individual soil attributes, except for nitrogen, were trained using MIR spectral data. Among the evaluated machine learning methods, Cubist produced the best results for most attributes, while the one-dimensional CNN was superior in predicting a few soil attributes. Complete MSE, R^2 , and MAE values for all evaluated models are provided in Table 4 in Appendix B.

Table 2. Best-performing models for each soil attribute based on R^2 score.

Variable	Spectral data	Machine learning method	R^2 score
Organic carbon (OC)	MIR	Cubist	0.9884
Total carbon (TC)	MIR	1D CNN	0.9879
Calcium carbonate (CaCO_3)	MIR	Cubist	0.9785
Cation exchange capacity (CEC)	MIR	Cubist	0.9272
Clay	MIR	1D CNN	0.9180
Sand	MIR	1D CNN	0.9122
Calcium (Ca)	MIR	1D CNN	0.9033
Nitrogen (N)	Vis-NIR	Cubist	0.8784
pH	MIR	1D CNN	0.8756
Water retention (WR)	MIR	Cubist	0.8580
Iron (Fe)	MIR	Cubist	0.8382
Silt	MIR	Cubist	0.8341
Magnesium (Mg)	MIR	Cubist	0.7880
Bulk density (BD)	MIR	1D CNN	0.7176
Electrical conductivity (EC)	MIR	Cubist	0.6972
Potassium (K)	MIR	Cubist	0.5274

4 Discussion

The results show that machine learning models trained on MIR spectral data are more accurate than models using Vis-NIR spectral data. This finding is supported by previous

studies (Madari et al. 2006, Safanelli et al. 2025), which showed that several fundamental and resolved absorption features from mineral and organic functional groups are contained in the MIR spectra. In contrast, Vis-NIR spectra contain overtones, weaker indirect signals from these fundamental vibrations, so they capture soil properties less clearly, which results in worse model performance compared to MIR. For most soil attributes, Cubist models performed the best, which can be attributed to their ability to combine rule-based partitioning with linear regression, making them well suited for capturing complex relationships in spectral data. One-dimensional CNN models achieved high predictive accuracy for a few soil attributes but were less consistent across all attributes compared to the Cubist method. The lower performance of machine learning models predicting electrical conductivity and potassium suggests that these attributes are harder to predict from spectral data only. Similar variability in prediction accuracy across different soil properties has been reported in previous studies (Dangal et al. 2019, Safanelli et al. 2025).

One limitation of this study is that models were trained on data from the KSSL and LUCAS datasets which contain samples collected in Europe and North America. These subsets were selected because most data points in the OSSL dataset are from Europe and North America. The soil types from these regions are the ones that are mostly represented in the OSSL, so this geographical limitation is inherent to the OSSL dataset rather than the choice of the subsets. This may affect the generalizability of the models to soil types in other regions and environmental conditions. The variability in performance of one-dimensional CNN models indicates that future work should explore further optimization of CNN architectures. In addition, expanding the dataset to incorporate more diverse soil types, exploring additional preprocessing techniques of spectral data, and evaluating other machine learning methods could improve model stability and overall predictive performance. Future research could also extend this approach to additional soil attributes not considered in this study.

5 Conclusion

This study demonstrates that soil spectroscopy combined with machine learning methods can serve as an efficient

alternative to the traditional laboratory approach for measuring soil attributes. High predictive accuracy ($R^2 > 0.90$) was achieved for several soil attributes, including organic carbon, total carbon, calcium carbonate, cation exchange capacity, clay, sand, and calcium, while electrical conductivity and potassium showed lower predictive performance ($R^2 < 0.70$). Machine learning models trained on MIR data outperformed those trained on Vis-NIR data for most soil attributes, and Cubist proved to be the most reliable method overall. The results of this paper show the potential for fast and cost-effective soil analysis approaches based on spectroscopy. Such methods can support agricultural management and environmental monitoring without the need for extensive laboratory analysis. Future work should focus on improving model robustness, expanding data sources, and reporting variability across validation folds or repeated training runs to better assess model stability and predictive performance.

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6 References

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Appendix A: Dataset characteristics

Table 3. Descriptive statistics of predicted soil attributes.

Soil attribute	Dataset	Variable	n	Mean	SD	Min	Median	Max	IQR
Clay	KSSL	clay.tot_usda.a334_w.pct	56433	24.34	17.61	0.00	21.85	100.00	23.60
	LUCAS	clay.tot_iso.11277_w.pct	23489	18.01	12.92	0.00	16.00	79.00	19.00
Sand	KSSL	sand.tot_usda.c60_w.pct	54996	38.45	28.91	0.00	33.10	100.00	48.70
	LUCAS	sand.tot_iso.11277_w.pct	23489	40.03	26.06	0.00	38.00	100.00	43.00
Silt	KSSL	silt.tot_usda.c62_w.pct	55049	37.28	20.62	0.00	37.10	256.00	32.30
	LUCAS	silt.tot_iso.11277_w.pct	23489	37.30	18.97	0.00	38.00	92.00	27.00
Organic carbon	KSSL	oc_usda.c729_w.pct	55900	4.22	9.88	0.00	0.98	65.60	2.28
	LUCAS	oc_iso.10694_w.pct	41023	4.62	8.36	0.01	2.05	58.68	2.65
Total carbon	KSSL	c.tot_usda.a622_w.pct	90229	6.51	12.77	0.00	1.50	78.45	3.37
Calcium carbonate	KSSL	caco3_usda.a54_w.pct	34850	7.32	12.85	0.00	1.04	101.37	9.20
	LUCAS	caco3_iso.10693_w.pct	40764	5.47	13.09	0.00	0.10	97.60	1.50
pH	KSSL	ph.h2o_usda.a268_index	59410	6.38	1.33	1.97	6.23	10.70	2.23
	LUCAS	ph.h2o_iso.10390_index	40764	6.16	1.35	3.17	6.13	10.37	2.50
Bulk density	KSSL	bd_usda.a4_g.cm3	42999	1.20	0.39	0.02	1.30	2.53	0.45
Electrical conductivity	KSSL	ec_usda.a364_ds.m	33790	2.80	12.01	0.00	0.24	313.13	0.73
	LUCAS	ec_iso.11265_ds.m	22032	0.28	0.40	0.00	0.17	9.69	0.19
Cation exchange capacity	KSSL	cec_usda.a723_cmolc.kg	57064	20.95	23.16	0.00	15.33	584.59	16.86
	LUCAS	cec_iso.11260_cmolc.kg	18982	15.78	14.46	1.00	12.40	234.00	13.30
Water retention	KSSL	wr.1500kPa_usda.a417_w.pct	41345	14.83	16.17	0.02	11.59	244.23	10.23
Nitrogen	KSSL	n.tot_usda.a623_w.pct	90244	0.33	0.62	0.00	0.12	41.90	0.22
	LUCAS	n.tot_iso.11261_w.pct	40764	0.30	0.37	0.00	0.19	3.86	0.19
Calcium	KSSL	ca.ext_usda.a722_cmolc.kg	57087	21.60	32.46	0.00	11.35	410.41	24.12
Potassium	KSSL	k.ext_usda.a725_cmolc.kg	97851	0.79	1.10	0.00	0.48	51.31	0.77
	LUCAS								
Iron	KSSL	fe.dith_usda.a66_w.pct	31138	1.24	1.60	0.00	0.82	28.44	1.23
Magnesium	KSSL	mg.ext_usda.a724_cmolc.kg	57095	5.24	8.17	0.00	2.72	172.64	5.53

Appendix B: Full model performance comparison

Table 4. Full performance results for all models based on MSE, R^2 , and MAE.

Variable	Dataset	KSSL			LUCAS (KSSL for TC and BD)		
	Spectrum	MIR			Vis-NIR		
	Algorithm Metric	PLSR	Cubist	1D CNN	PLSR	Cubist	1D CNN
Clay	MSE	27.8636	24.3651	21.5787	53.3397	41.6384	80.3409
	R^2	0.8932	0.9066	0.9180	0.6730	0.7448	0.4901
	MAE	3.4983	3.0304	2.9718	5.3695	4.5917	6.6687
Sand	MSE	100.4729	84.5605	73.7251	361.4869	287.3377	487.3390
	R^2	0.8811	0.8999	0.9122	0.4613	0.5718	0.2935
	MAE	7.0983	6.3944	6.0034	15.0485	13.0779	18.2488
Silt	MSE	83.5002	69.0338	75.3483	185.0162	147.8943	292.0404
	R^2	0.7994	0.8341	0.8197	0.4846	0.5880	0.1783
	MAE	6.5941	5.9256	6.3479	10.7880	9.4352	13.8991
Organic carbon (OC)	MSE	2.3013	1.1294	1.4824	11.7385	5.6669	12.6923
	R^2	0.9764	0.9884	0.9844	0.8322	0.9190	0.8218
	MAE	0.8739	0.3883	0.6354	2.1355	1.1447	1.8442
Total carbon (TC)	MSE	3.8151	2.3788	2.2286	40.8611	16.4963	25.2573
	R^2	0.9793	0.9871	0.9879	0.8687	0.9470	0.9202
	MAE	1.1228	0.6254	0.6684	4.5548	2.1385	2.7913
Calcium carbonate (CaCO ₃)	MSE	4.2211	3.7491	4.8004	19.9761	16.0092	65.7618
	R^2	0.9758	0.9785	0.9711	0.8841	0.9071	0.6119
	MAE	0.9047	0.7139	1.1490	2.5763	1.6443	4.4098
pH	MSE	0.2861	0.2355	0.2194	0.2583	0.2659	0.4851
	R^2	0.8365	0.8654	0.8756	0.8583	0.8541	0.7339
	MAE	0.3965	0.3508	0.3510	0.3877	0.3911	0.5534
Bulk density (BD)	MSE	0.0596	0.0511	0.0479	0.0778	0.0720	0.0687
	R^2	0.6477	0.6978	0.7176	0.5545	0.5882	0.6165
	MAE	0.1719	0.1630	0.1695	0.2218	0.2062	0.2092
Electrical conductivity (EC)	MSE	74.0131	46.1173	55.1476	0.0653	0.0650	0.0952
	R^2	0.5140	0.6972	0.6109	0.4138	0.4167	0.2270
	MAE	4.0101	1.7144	2.6483	0.1482	0.1289	0.1596
Cation exchange capacity (CEC)	MSE	56.8139	40.3720	41.2832	82.3397	53.3902	169.1123
	R^2	0.8975	0.9272	0.9247	0.5869	0.7321	0.2354
	MAE	3.9520	2.5240	3.6105	5.3784	4.1838	8.3079
Water retention (WR)	MSE	46.6647	37.4089	48.9910	-	-	-
	R^2	0.8229	0.8580	0.8039	-	-	-
	MAE	3.4358	2.5010	4.4444	-	-	-
Nitrogen (N)	MSE	0.0923	0.0830	0.0525	0.0322	0.0165	0.0376
	R^2	0.7900	0.8112	0.8678	0.7629	0.8784	0.7285
	MAE	0.1005	0.0644	0.0877	0.1147	0.0707	0.1185
Calcium (Ca)	MSE	127.5696	112.4509	101.4416	-	-	-
	R^2	0.8843	0.8981	0.9033	-	-	-
	MAE	6.0577	4.4518	4.8121	-	-	-
Potassium (K)	MSE	0.5691	0.5056	0.6064	0.9418	0.9001	1.0119
	R^2	0.4681	0.5274	0.4653	0.2825	0.3143	0.1537
	MAE	0.4169	0.3024	0.3709	0.5194	0.4352	0.5200
Iron (Fe)	MSE	0.5253	0.4115	0.5556	-	-	-
	R^2	0.7935	0.8382	0.7820	-	-	-
	MAE	0.4273	0.3306	0.4338	-	-	-
Magnesium (Mg)	MSE	19.6128	14.7205	15.1165	-	-	-
	R^2	0.7175	0.7880	0.7732	-	-	-
	MAE	2.5136	1.6932	2.0819	-	-	-